

Women, Marriage and Modernity in Shazaf Fatima Haider's *How It Happened*: A Postcolonial Feminist Study

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**A Research Article on Postcolonial Feminism in Humanities
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Abstract

This article uses Chandra Talpade Mohanty's postcolonial feminist theory to analyze how women, marriage, and modernity are portrayed in Shazaf Fatima Haider's novel *How It Happened*. Mohanty calls for contextual, historically grounded, and pluralistic feminist praxis in response to the Western feminist construction of "Third World women" as a homogenous, passive, and victimized group. The study highlights the diversity of the female characters such as Dadi, Saleha, and Zeba in terms of age, social status, faith, and autonomy by using this paradigm.

Pivotal scenes like Zeba's vocal refusal of home duties, Dadi's sarcastic remarks about love, and the humorous generational conflict showcase how the system of arranged marriages upholds patriarchal and postcolonial social standards. At the same time, the novel's humor and female solidarity serve as decolonizing tools by defending individual liberty, opposing the cultural advertising of women, and opposing categorical classifications. Haider's work embodies Mohanty's call for a non-homogenizing, culturally aware, and solidarity-based feminism that reimagines marriage as a space of cultural and emotional decolonization, one in which women's agency is historically grounded, personally expressed, and supported by the community.

Keywords: *postcolonial feminism, non-homogenizing, third world women*

Introduction

The novel *How It Happened* satirically depicts the changing landscape of marriage, gender, and modernity in contemporary Pakistani society. The story, narrated by fifteen-year-old Saleha, unfolds within a Shia “Bandian” family in Karachi where inter-sectarian alliances, arranged marriages, and love are the main causes of generational rivalry.

Since then, the text has attracted scholarly interest. Haider breaks down binary gender stereotypes allowing women from different generations like Dadi, Saleha and Zeba to challenge patriarchal marriage structures in decolonized ways, according to a postcolonial feminist interpretation. Others highlight the struggle between tradition and modernization, especially through Zeba’s vocal opposition to arranged marriage and household duties, illuminating how her work balances cultural continuity with modern values.

The present paper uses Chandra Talpade Mohanty’s postcolonial feminist theory, which advocates for contextual specificity, intersectionality, and collective agency in place of reductive narratives about “Third-World women,” to examine this relationship. Instead of being a flat depiction of victims, Haider’s characters are revealed as complex individuals who are influenced by religion, generation, class, and individual desires.

The novel’s pivotal moments such as Zeba’s rebellious declaration, “*I don’t cook... I don’t want to get married,*” against Dadi’s patriarchal order, “*Sensible Bandian women... do our duty,*” and the final inter-sect marriage. These moments reveal marriage as both a site of feminist negotiation and a structure shaped by patriarchal and colonial legacies. Haider reconfigures marriage as a contested institution in which emotional autonomy becomes possible. through satire, generational struggle, and female solidarity.

In this article, I argue that Mohanty's idea of a situated, non-homogenizing feminism, one that opposes cultural imperialism, recovers marital agency, and promotes unity via common, situation-specific female experiences is best represented by *How It Happened*. The book honors women's ability to negotiate and reclaim marriage within the changing context of contemporary Pakistani identity rather than confining Pakistani femininity to a single archetype.

1. Literature Review

This review examines existing scholarship on gender, marriage, and modernity, and situates the novel within a postcolonial feminist framework. The body of research on Shazaf Fatima Haider's *How It Happened* and places it in a postcolonial feminist context. It identifies gaps, assesses important studies according to their theoretical foundation, analytical depth and relevance, as well as lays out the groundwork for implementing Mohanty's theory of contextual, non-homogenizing feminism.

A postcolonial feminist interpretation of *How It Happened* is provided by Sami et al. (2025), who focus on the binary representation of women as either "obedient" or "rebellious." Dadi's claim that "good girls marry boys of their mothers' choice" demonstrates how patriarchal customs institutionalize emotional confinement. Despite their insightful textual criticism, this study attempts to close this gap by utilizing Mohanty's focus on individual situatedness to examine the complex heterogeneity among female characters.

Complementary to this, Qamar and Shaheen (2024) examine how love and interfaith (Shia-Sunni) interactions are presented in the book. They argue focusing on Simone de Beauvoir, that these connections serve as "progressive ruptures" that alter long-standing family and sectarian systems. Their approach, however, falls short of addressing feminist theories that emphasize contextual solidarity and collective agency, two elements that are essential to Mohanty's paradigm (Qamar & Shaheen, 2024).

Meanwhile, Imran et al. (2022) focuses on household customs, such as Mayun, zang-bharai and kitchen duties, and how this supports patriarchal authority. Their analysis shows how gendered hierarchies are reinforced by the novel's realistic portrayal of daily life. However, instead of examining female agency or resistance inside those places, they frequently place more emphasis on replicating patriarchal standards, which leaves potential for a more nuanced feminist perspective.

To understand generational conflict surrounding arranged weddings, Ishfaq et al. (2022) integrate sociological concepts from Mannheim and Giddens. They contend that Zeba's revolt reflects more general contemporary goals colliding with conventional limitations. Although their analysis effectively places the work in a larger societal framework, it does not specifically address how marriage operates as a gendered, contested space of resistance and power (Ishfaq et al., 2022).

Haider's deliberate code-switching between Urdu and English is noted in the 2022 article in the International RASD Journal as an example of how Pakistani middle-class women are forming hybrid identities. Although this piece sheds light on the expressive aspect of cultural identity, it makes no connection between these linguistic decisions and feminist resistance or marriage-related concerns.

Finally, Zahid et al. (2023), employing a postmodern lens, argues that Haider subverts large narratives by emphasizing localized, human experiences. Their insightful analysis of narrative structure leaves room for more research because they do not overtly link this subversion to marriage or gender.

Among the existing studies, Sami et al. (2025) come closest to engaging Mohanty's postcolonial feminist critique, addressing her cautions against homogenizing "Third World women," even though other studies use wide feminist frameworks. However, even this study tends to generalize the experiences of women. One ongoing gap is that, in contrast to what Mohanty's theory would require, none of the current interpretations consider marriage as a place of colonial heritage, patriarchal oppression, and communal emotional negotiation.

To close this gap, my research uses Mohanty's viewpoint to show how "*How It Happened*" presents female protagonists as contextually placed individuals whose relationships across class, generation, and sect create a web of solidarity rather than as simple archetypes. I contend that the book reinterprets marriage as a transforming, decolonizing space where women regain their independence via comedy, interfaith cooperation, and intergenerational communication, rather than just as an institution to be criticized. By highlighting complexity, grounded solidarity, and emotional agency in postcolonial Pakistan, Haider's story satisfies Mohanty's appeal for placed, non-homogenizing feminist approach.

2. Thesis Statement

How It Happened reflects Mohanty's concept of historically situated, non-homogenizing feminism by presenting marriage as a disputed space influenced by sect, class, and generation. The story exposes patriarchal and colonial legacies in arranged marriages through the distinctive voices of Dadi, Saleha, and Zeba. It offers a decolonized vision of marital modernity based on relational agency and local specificity, redefining marriage as a place of emotional reclamation and group solidarity.

3. Research Objectives

1. To examine how Mohanty's idea of situated variety is exhibited by female characters influenced by generation, class, sect, and desire, by defying stereotypes of Pakistani women.
2. To explore how interfaith, arranged, and love-based marriages function as sites of feminist resistance and emotional autonomy cultural colonial conventions, as well as patriarchal systems.
3. To analyze how Haider highlights patriarchal/colonial standards and ordinary female revolt through rituals, discourse, and family dynamics in her use of satire and domestic realism.
4. To contextualize how the novel's emphasis on class, generation, identity, and sect relates to Mohanty's need for contextualized feminist praxis.

4. Research Questions

1. How does Haider present Dadi, Saleha, and Zeba as examples of Mohanty's situated diversity, challenges stereotypes of Pakistani women?
2. How do love-based, arranged, and interfaith marriages function as vehicles for patriarchy while also providing a platform for feminist activism and emotional independence?
3. In what ways does Haider's use of domestic realism and satire through speech, rituals, and family dynamics expose and subvert long-standing colonial and patriarchal norms?
4. In what ways does Zeba and Saleha's solidarity serve as relational agency, embodying a postcolonial feminist praxis that is contextualized?

5. Theoretical Framework

This study draws on Chandra Talpade Mohanty's postcolonial feminist theory, which advocates a culturally grounded and relational feminist praxis while criticizing the universalizing inclinations of Western feminism, particularly its depiction of a homogenous "Third-World woman." This framework includes:

5.1. Situated Diversity, Double Colonization, and Narrative Resistance

This study draws on Chandra Talpade Mohanty's concept of situated diversity, which rejects the homogenization of "Third World women" and instead emphasizes that women's experiences are historically grounded and shaped by intersecting identities such as class, sect, generation, and locality. This framework directly informs the analysis of female characters in *How It Happened* as contextually positioned subjects rather than universalized figures. In alignment with this, standpoint epistemology strengthens the study's approach by asserting that marginalized individuals possess epistemic privilege with a distinctive awareness of hierarchical power relations derived from lived experience. This perspective enables the examination of narrative voice and female consciousness as sources of critical insight into gendered power structures operating within marriage and family systems.

Building on this foundation, Mohanty's concept of double colonization provides a lens for interpreting marriage as a site where colonial legacies intersect with indigenous patriarchal norms. The novel's representation of domestic customs, sectarian expectations, and generational tensions is therefore analyzed as part of a broader structure of layered oppression and negotiation. Mohanty's notion of intersectional solidarity further aligns with the study's objective by highlighting forms of collective agency that emerge across differences of class, sect, and generation. Finally, the use of satire, domestic realism, and standpoint narration is examined as a narrative strategy that subverts to dominant patriarchal and colonial discourses. Together, these interconnected theoretical strands establish a coherent framework for analyzing marriage, gendered agency, and narrative resistance within the novel.

6. Analysis

Through the viewpoint of fifteen-year-old Saleha Bandian, Shazaf Fatima Haider's 2013 humorous novel *How It Happened* parodies the traditions of arranged marriage in a traditional Pakistani household. Using the postcolonial feminist framework developed by Chandra Talpade Mohanty, we examine the novel and demonstrate how its narrative enacts a contextual, non-homogenizing feminism. Novel quotes are connected to Mohanty's ideas in each of the following sections. Generally speaking, Bandian women are not portrayed as a single type of "third world woman," but rather as unique individuals with agency within their cultural setting. The female protagonists in the novel speak from their own unique perspectives, marriage is portrayed as a site of dual oppression (double colonialism), and the author challenges patriarchal conventions through comedy and everyday realism. Through the positioned voice of the narrator, Saleha, the story emphasizes marriage as a site of double colonization, promotes female relational agency, and considers modernity as both a disturbance and a desire.

According to Mohanty, *How It Happened* offers each woman her unique voice and "agency" within her setting, whereas Western feminism frequently erases women's distinctions and voices.

6.1. Marriage as a Site of Double Colonization:

How It Happened echoes Mohanty's idea of women's "double colonization" by patriarchy and imperialism by portraying arranged marriage as a system that functions as both cultural tradition and patriarchal control.

For instance, a family elder angrily denounces a young woman: "It's a Scandal! Why, a woman has only two things in this society: her ability to bear sons and her reputation!" This comment demonstrates the patriarchal mentality that colonizes women's identities by reducing a woman's worth of honor and reproduction. Similarly, someone yells, "*She love-married*," when Saleha overhears family members chatting about a love marriage. She was a shameless creature; her father was never allowed to appear in public again, and her mother attempted suicide! She brought her family so much disgrace (*p.8*).

Both instances demonstrate how marriage is an institution in which religious and familial honor dictate women's bodies and decisions. Mohanty argues that women in postcolonial contexts are shaped by the intersecting pressures of patriarchy and colonial modernity.

In this context, arranged marriage is represented as an institution shaped by both patriarchal norms and the historical legacies of colonial modernity, tying the women to the “honor-shame” code and the lineage. As a result, marriage is portrayed in Haider’s novel as a site of double colonization, enforcing patriarchal gender roles (such as “bear sons and reputation”) and evoking patriarchal norms (such as prohibiting love and demanding dowries). This supports Mohanty’s criticism that such double oppression is frequently overlooked in Western representations. Instead, Haider’s writing exposes it through the family’s long-standing traditions and radicalism of the grandmother.

6.2. Situated, Contextual Female Identities

Instead of portraying every female character as a stereotypical “Eastern woman,” Haider shows them as context specific. Saleha, her older sister Zeba, her daughter-in-law Saima, and her grandma Dadi all have unique personalities and perspectives on marriage. Mohanty highlights the need for feminist analysis to acknowledge the cultural diversity of women. Zeba, for example, defiantly defies conventional norms:

Once Zeba says out loud: “*I don’t cook. I don’t like children. I don’t want to get married*” (p.107). Even in the conservative home, Zeba’s firm, contemporary stance sets her apart from her submissive siblings. Zeba, on the other hand, is portrayed with pride and admiration by Saleha, and according to the narrator her sister is both her generation’s heroin and the nightmare for previous generation.

Together, these two quotations demonstrate how each girl has a distinct identity: Dadi is the adamant traditionalist reprimanding them, Saleha is the younger witness, and Zeba is a rebellious nonconformist. Each woman’s actions reflect her unique combination of personality, religion, and familial background; the narrative never puts them into a single stereotype. Mohanty’s emphasis on situated knowledge is exemplified by this diversity of voices, which convey “where (the women) are, where they stand, who they are.”

Haider embodies a context-aware feminism, as Mohanty contends third-world feminism must be, by allowing room for Zeb’s direct rejection and Saleha's unique viewpoint.

6.3. Regional Agency

As opposed to being isolated individuals, Haider's characters frequently find agency in their relationships and collective rebellions. Mohanty's theory that women's empowerment is culturally and collectively related is in line with this relational agency. Resistance is most effective in large quantities, according to Saleha: "*It was always better to rebel in company than alone*" As a character in George Orwell's 1948 novel *Nineteen Eighty-Four* suggests, how the girls stand by one other in the face of the strict familial traditions. For instance, Saleha and Zeba conspire to control their grandmother's ire when Haroon, Saleha's brother, discreetly pursues his own suitor.

The defiance of each sister gives the others more confidence. Saleha establishes the tone for the younger girls' independence by praising Zeba, her "heroine." This illustrates how networks of friendship and kinship can give rise to agencies. Mohanty also criticizes the idea of isolated "victims" in Western feminism, emphasizing that "differences between women... should be used as strengths to create a community." This is embodied in Haider's book: the Bandian women's jokes and plots are relational strategies of female disobedience rather than isolated protests.

6.4. Modernity as Disruption and Aspiration

The struggle in the narrative revolves around the tension between tradition and modernity. Modernity is portrayed as a place of potential independence, especially for young women, as well as a danger to family values. While seniors like Dadi maintain tradition and compliance, characters like Zeba and Saleha lean toward contemporary ideals of choice, autonomy, and emotional honesty. Any departure elicits a harsh and acerbic response from Dadi: "*Hai Hai, Allah ... My own granddaughter is acting like a prostitute behind my back!*" (p.201)

The elder generations' fear of losing cultural control is highlighted by such exaggeration. Modernity is not portrayed as a one-dimensional positive, though; it also carries the risk of estrangement, confusion, and worry. Haider's story deftly demonstrates that modernism is a reassessment of inherited standards rather than a complete rejection of tradition. In a similar vein, Mohanty cautions against confusing modernity with Westernization. Rather, she promotes a decolonized modernity that emerges from the cultural logic of society itself. According to this

interpretation, *How It Happened* promotes culturally grounded modernism, where women rethink their responsibilities without cutting their ties to their heritage.

6.5. Satire and Domestic Realism as Feminist Resistance

In line with Mohanty's concept of contextualized feminist discourse, *How It Happened* critiques patriarchy through humor and genuine home detail. By making readers laugh, the book dismantles repressive traditions. Saleha's fictitious indignation over bridal clothing serves as a striking illustration: "*Let me tell you now before you protest, you will wear a Sehra of roses when you come, I don't care what you say!*" ... "*No one wears a Sehra! A curtain of roses covering my face... What will I look like? ...and I don't want to wear those abominable shoes: the sleem shahees that are curled at the end? I'll look like a relic from the past!*" (p.92).

The traditional bridal veil (called "Sehra") and pointed shoes are made fun of in this exchange, in which a granddaughter criticizes her grandmother (Dadi Jan). Haider undermines the authority of these traditions by presenting them in all their ridiculousness (bridal roses, "relic" shoes). Mohanty calls for feminist resistance that analyzes Third World women's situation with subtlety rather than "exoticizing" them as defenseless victims.

Haider accomplishes this through satire: Saleha's sardonic remarks and the work's realistic portrayal of domestic life make severe persecution seem like common humor. By doing this, the novel challenges readers in Pakistan to acknowledge and consider patriarchy from a cultural perspective. In summary, the situational humor and "whimsical" nature of the novel (as one reviewer puts it) is its feminist praxis; instead of portraying women as tragic objects, it laughs at oppression from within.

6.6. Standpoint Epistemology

Lastly, by giving a Pakistani girl's perspective more weight, *How It Happened* demonstrates Mohanty's demand for viewpoint epistemology. Since Saleha narrates the story in the first person, everything that happens is interpreted through her perspective. Saleha, for instance, informs us that she views Zeba as "her generations heroine," clearly interpreting family events in terms of generations. Everything is "situated" from Saleha's point of view; thus, the reader never views the household through the eyes of an outsider or a neutral narrator.

This echoes Mohanty's contention that women in the Third World should be allowed to speak for themselves rather than having Western academics speak for them.

7. Conclusion

Through its depictions of marriage, female identity, agency, and solidarity in modern Pakistani society, Shazaf Fatima Haider's *How It Happened* aims to investigate how Chandra Talpade Mohanty's vision of postcolonial feminist praxis is reflected and enacted. This study used Mohanty's ideas of situated diversity, double colonization, relational agency, and standpoint epistemology to highlight how the novel resists both patriarchal structures and Western feminist generalizations. This was done in response to a critical gap in existing scholarship, which frequently ignores nuanced, theory-informed feminist readings of Haider's work.

This analysis suggests that *How It Happened* presents a culturally grounded form of feminist resistance when read through Mohanty's framework. The novel emphasizes Pakistani women's ability to challenge, negotiate, and modify inherited norms often through humor, community, and ordinary language instead of depicting them as helpless victims. By doing this, Haider reinterprets marriage, tradition, and modernity as malleable and changeable concepts, supporting Mohanty's proposal for a plural, historically grounded, and socially sensitive feminism.

In conclusion, the study I conducted confirms that *How It Happened* is a postcolonial feminist narrative that exemplifies the kinds of grounded, communal, and culturally relevant tactics required to subvert oppressive systems from within. It is not only a humorous book.

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